

History, significance and theme of International Day of Mathematics 2023

August 24, 2023

1 introduction

Pi Day 2023; March 14 represent the value of $\pi(3.14)$ for those people who follows the month or date format.

Pi Day : Archimedes of Syracuse was the first mathematician who calculated the value of π .

The value of π (3.14).international day of mathematics or pi Day is celebrate on 14th march to define the mathematical constant , π which tells us the ratio of a circular circumferences to its diameter.

To recognize or appreciate the value of mathematics in our daily lives the mathematics enthusiasts celebrate it around the globe .to promotes the mathematics education and awareness the pi Day celebrates in various school colleges and universities and also mathematics organization globally with an aim and unique theme.

2 Theme

“Mathematics for everyone” is the theme of Pi Day 2023 according to the official website of the celebration, that is proposed by Marco Zarco rotario from Philippines’ trece Martires city national high school.

3 History

In 1988 a physicist Larry Shaw he organized a large-scale celebration at the San Francisco Exploratorium in the United States .by cutting a pi shape pie they held first celebration and maintain the value of pi in many decimal places as possible . Archimedes of Syracuse named mathematician first calculated the value of pi and Leonhard Euler used the symbol of Pi in 1737 accepted by the scientific community.

In 2019 pi day was observed as international mathematics day by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) in its 40th General Conference.

4 Significance

Pi is irrational and transcendental number and its decimal representative values were never ends and never repeats.how ever its original value does not known and the area or circumfrances of a circle can never find. the pyramids of Giza were built on the principles of pi People believed in Egypt . The ratio between the height of the pyramids and the perimeter of their base is the same as that between a circle's radius and circumferenc.

To appreciate the importance of mathematics in our daily life the pi day is celebrated . . Pi is a fundamental constant having a significant in performing calculation in mathematics used by scientists.

Its is also considered that the birth anniversary of scientist Albert Einstein. Widely renowned theoretical physicist Stephen Hawking were also died on this day in 2018.